

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

THE CONCEPT OF "NATIONAL IDENTITY" AND "NATIONAL SPIRIT" IN THE LITERARY AND PEDAGOGICAL ACTIVITY OF ISMAYIL SHIKHLI

Zeynalova A.

Researcher

Institute of Philosophy and Sociology; Azerbaijan National Academy of Sciences;

Republic of Azerbaijan

ORCID ID: 0009-0006-4679-0855

ABSTRACT

Ismayil Shikhli, one of the prominent representatives of Azerbaijani literature, prose writer, literary critic, publicist, writer, screenwriter, member of the Union of writers of Azerbaijan, deputy of the Supreme Soviet of the Republic of Azerbaijan and prominent teacher, is attracted special attention to the origin of his art from the people's spirit, the origin of our national-spiritual existence in his works.

The article is important from the point of view of determining the national and spiritual basis of Ismayil Shikhli's creativity, which played an important role in the Azerbaijani literature of the XX century, especially in the development of prose. Those who want to study the sources of Ismail Shikhli's prose, the full essence of his worldview and Idea aesthetic principles, with which he is associated as a national writer, can benefit from the results of this study as a source.

Relevance of the topic: Nowadays, the special importance of the problems of national identity, historical memory, return to national and spiritual values makes it even more urgent to draw attention to this topic.

Keywords: national identity, pedagogy, Ismayil Shikhli, Azerbaijan, national identity.

INTRODUCTION

The creativity of the national writer Ismayil Shikhli (1919-1995), one of the prominent figures of Azerbaijani literature of the XX century, is distinguished by the breadth of the subject scope of ideas, the richness of the world of images, the vitality of the language style, the original style of narration, as well as strong attachment to the spirit of the people.

The fact that the master artist, who created invaluable examples of colorful, creative prose, from small-scale stories to such a huge, monumental novel as "Dali Kur", throughout the whole landscape of his work was connected with the people's morality, the mentality qualities coming from the depths of the national spirit and memory, made him a writer of the people literally. In this regard, along with all other creative qualities, Ismayil Shikhli's art originates from the spirit of the people, the creation of our national-spiritual existence in his works, the close connection of the images he created with historical-spiritual memory, with the genetics of leyk and other such issues attract special attention. In fact, as an artist, he was brought up directly on the fertile ground of folk spirituality and national spirit. The whole essence of this writer, all his extraordinary power, is associated with the strength of the folk spirit, expressed in his works.

In the current situation, the special importance of the problems of national identity, historical memory return to national and spiritual values makes it even more urgent to draw attention to this topic. For the first time in the presented article, The problem of national self-expression in Ismayil Shikhli's work was systematically investigated and the writer's attitude to national-spiritual sources and historical identity was evaluated from a scientific-theoretical point of view.

The national character of Ismail Shikhli's prose was analyzed within a single context, tracing both the

structure of the writer's story and the moral-historical genetics of various images.

The national character and images in the writer's stories and novels were compared with their adequacy in our spiritual historical memory, and the qualitative innovations carried out by the creative imagination during the use of national-spiritual resources were clarified. When creating images of Jahandar Aga and this rash, the peculiarities of the writer's approach to spiritual and historical memory were revealed and those aspects were characterized as high artistic qualities.

In order to enhance the color and dynamism of the plot in Ismail Shikhly's prose, the network and nature of the converted samples of folk art (proverb, parable, anecdote, bayati, couplet, narration, legend, etc.) were determined and the artistic, stylistic and ideological-aesthetic function performed by them was scientifically analyzed.

It should be noted that Ismayil Shikhli's father was also a teacher, and his opening eyes in the family of teachers did not affect the thinking of Ismayil Shikhli and then determined his life path in general. "Teaching" has always been the most important task of Ismayil Shikhli and has also become a quality reflecting his nature and content of his activity. It was because of these features that those around him would call him "Ismail teacher."

The complex socio-political conditions of the 1930s, the Second World War, the events of the post-war stage, undoubtedly, played a certain role in strengthening the character of İ. Shikhli: the great personality of the future lived from the 30s to the 50s as the most intense period of his life. The 30s were the first stage of İ. Shikhli's "self-awareness"- at that stage he sometimes wrote emotional poems, sometimes kept sentimental diaries and sometimes fantasized about the logic of the events taking place around him. It seems

that the fronts of the war did not manage to do his "romantic world", although they edited it a little.

After the war, İ. Shikhli again plunged into his "romantic world" for some time: he wrote his first stories, essays, studied world literature more deeply and his writer-teacher character was formed on the basis of a strange contact between romanticism and realism.

Comparing the beginning, formation stage of Ismail Shikhli prose and the mature, perfect period, the process of deep and comprehensive development in terms of mastery is clearly visible. Along with these, another aspect is prominently noticeable. And this is due to the fact that in adulthood, in the wise ages of his life, the writer is more focused on topics from folklore motives, historical and genetic memory. His historical and ethnographic stories, his famous series of "Legends and stories", his artistic and journalistic writings dedicated to the problems of national self-realization appeared not by chance.

Thus, in the novel "My Dying World" we are witnessing a clear expression of what position Ismail Shikhli chose as a writer, what literary and aesthetic task he took on. Ismail Shikhli thought about the fate of his people with every work he wrote after knowing and understanding himself and his word in literary life and creative world. He breathed with the people, lived with the spirit of the people. For this reason, the successful artistic reflection of national self-expression in Ismail Shikhli's work and its manifestation in various forms is a natural and legitimate phenomenon.

It should also be noted that national self-expression—a set of qualities of the spirit of the people, historical memory, norms of morality and behavior, mentality, system of moral values in general—is in the writer's artistic world a theme-motive, idea-content, language, image, plot, this is the artistic embodiment of levels. In the works of Ismail Shikhli, this embodiment is reflected in the following forms:

- giving a wide place to moral values reflecting national norms of morality and behavior;
- creation of national character images and national characters;
- historical ethnic memory, national self-awareness, national identity problems in various artistic means and methods;
- consistent, systematic appeal and commitment to folklore.

In addition, moral values reflecting the norms of national morality and behavior are realized in the works of the writer mainly in two directions:

1. In the ideas and aesthetic views demonstrated by the writer himself in prose;
2. In the behavior and psychology of images, as well as in the linguistic layers of the image language with an inherent color.

Speaking about the moral values reflecting the norms of national morality and behavior manifested in his ideological and aesthetic views, first of all, it is necessary to mention that he is a wise and national-spirited person by nature. Ismail Shikhli, who is distinguished by his patient, restrained and sensitive attitude to life, events and processes around him, as well as to those

with whom he communicates, lives in memories, memories as a kind, brave, self-centered, far-sighted person, was able to create his national spirit, bright and wise image with his life and activities outside his creativity. Those who know him remember well that the nationality of Ismail Shikhli and the wisdom of Ismail Shikhli are the main and leading factors.

Heavy behavior, proud gait, heartfelt manner of speech reflecting the sweetness of the people, deep content, which spoke about various aspects and problems of our national and spiritual values, historical resources, our wisdom were various images of the inner spirit, the wisdom of the people concentrated in his nature. With his personality, worldview and foresight, he literally rose to the floor of a bright intellectual, wise national elder, worthy of his nation and people. In the works written by the writer, who possessed such a natural nature and national spirit, of course, the vivid expression of that great spirit should have been reflected. In this sense, we can boldly say that nationality, creativity and wisdom in the prose of Ismail Shikhli come directly from the personality of Ismail Shikhli. The founder of this personality is the spirit of the people, folklore memory and historical and ethnic culture.

In his work, the writer draws attention to the factors and conditions that are important for national-spiritual existence with the example events and images brought from the historical past and national memory. Therefore, the most prominent aspect of his artistic work is that it is based on national and spiritual values and that his pen and talent are fighting for these values with all their might.

It should be noted that it is not without reason that in the philosophy of Ismail Shikhli the realities of historical memory and the values of national mentality, morality, behavior are manifested in the actions of the images created by the writer. The values in question are imprinted on the consciousness and thought of the bearer of the national self as an incorruptible, unchanging inscription. The laws of national morality and historical identity are here the judge-absolute. The fateful steps taken by the images in relation to the expression and self-determination of national identity are guided by these laws. Even the most powerful and omnipotent personality-images are not capable of opposing these laws. In this case, the image is also able to experience a sharp psychological shock in the spiritual space where national-moral laws reign—in his own feelings and thoughts.

The protection of historical ethnographic memory and national and spiritual values has always worried Ismail Shikhli. What disasters the neglect and alienation of the national-spiritual memory led him to worry as an artist of the translation of the people's spirit, he repeatedly returned to this problem in his works. In his novels and stories, the writer's anxiety about detachment from the national-spiritual memory, alienation is clearly felt. Ismail Shikhli sees the roots of our national and spiritual tragedies in indifference to ourselves and our historical memory.

RESULT

One of the prominent figures in the history of Azerbaijani literature Ismail Shikhli was respected not

only as a talented writer, but also as a public and political figure, publicist and translator. Perhaps, on the basis of the fact that he has all these opportunities, he is a talented teacher with special pedagogical skills. I. Shikhli was, first of all, a creative person. His creative laboratory is distinguished by the richness of its scope. All this is confirmed by the novels reflecting the way of life, life, culture, education and moral and spiritual values of the Azerbaijani people within a certain historical space and time.

National writer Ismail Shikhli is one of the brightest literary figures who brought innovation to modern Azerbaijani literature. A thousand close ties to our rich literary traditions, folklore memory, high mastery of the subtleties of prose poetics, the ability to embody the specific artistic in his works gave him a literary identity in our literature. I. Shikhli protected patriotic feelings and civic pride in life as well as in art and exalted it above all. The fact that in his work the expressions are simple, the meaning is clear, but at the same time philosophical confirms that I. Shikhli is connected with the people's memory and the people's spirit. In all his works, this memory and keeping of the soul in the head serve to make a person appear in the civic ampoule, fight, turn the national feeling into eternal duty.

We would also like to note that Ismail Shikhli is one of the literary personalities who, with his creativity and originality of talent, became a great event of Azerbaijani prose. As a citizen writer, who created the highest artistic examples of Azerbaijani prose in his unique artistic image, distinguished by the breadth of his intellectual capabilities, devoted his intellect to his native people, his great ideals, he fulfilled his duty to the

motherland and art with honor. In the creative power of the great writer, in the wonder of his artistic activity, poetic perfection, simplicity and clarity of his language come to the fore as determining merits. The beauty of language testifies to the more grandiose aspects of the writer's artistic activity. The writer's sweet speech, pleasant style of utterance, successful forms of idioms, each word-image epithet, comparison, metaphor, or various stylistic figures are behind the whole concept of figurative perception of reality by the word artist and his expression in appropriate ways. I. Shikhli's fame as a writer and gaining many fans is primarily due to his ability to use the rich Azerbaijani language.

All the nuances listed above in the article contribute to a deep understanding of the concept of national identity, national spirit in the literary and pedagogical activity of Ismail Shikhli and also reflect the philosophical world of the writer and educator.

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